

THE ROLE OF SONGS IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract:

This article analyzes the role of songs in teaching English in primary grades. The research results show that songs are an important tool for increasing children's interest in the process of language learning, developing pronunciation and listening skills, and expanding vocabulary. The article also examines the possibilities of forming students' communicative competence and increasing their confidence in communication with the help of songs. During the study, the effectiveness of songs was assessed based on the analysis of scientific articles, observations, and practical experiments.

Key words: primary school, English language, songs, communicative competence, pronunciation, vocabulary.

Introduction

In today's era of globalization, the improvement of the process of teaching foreign languages, in particular, English, is of great importance. Especially in primary grades, the use of effective teaching methods plays an important role in increasing students' interest in language and its faster acquisition. The use of songs in this process is recognized as an effective way to develop students' speech and listening skills, increase their vocabulary, and form a positive attitude towards language. Songs facilitate the process of language learning through rhythm and melody, improve students' pronunciation, and naturally help them master grammar and lexical units. In addition, songs contribute to the formation of students' communicative competence, developing their ability to feel the language. In this article, the role of songs in teaching English in primary grades is analyzed, and their effectiveness is scientifically and practically substantiated.

The purpose of the article is to study the methods of effective use of songs in teaching English in primary grades and to highlight their importance in the educational process on a scientific basis. In the course of the research, methods of analysis of scientific sources, observation, and practical experience are used. The results confirm that songs are an effective didactic tool for primary school students in learning a foreign language.

Main part

Scientific research on the use of songs in teaching English in primary grades shows that musical materials serve as an effective tool in the process of language learning. According to research by psycholinguists and educators, children tend to learn language in a natural environment, that is, through context, and songs play an important role in this process (Gardner, 1983; Krashen, 1985). There are many scientific works proving that children learn language faster through rhythm, song, and play. For example, in Fonmayer's (2006) research, it is emphasized that songs play an important role in the formation of listening and pronunciation skills. Penfield and Roberts (1959) noted that young children acquire pronunciation faster and more accurately than adults, which indicates the possibility of developing phonetic competence through songs.

Researchers such as Cameron (2001) and Brewster, Ellis & Girard (2002) deeply analyzed the role of songs in the educational process in their works. As a result of their research, it was found that songs strengthen children's memory and contribute to the natural acquisition of grammar and vocabulary. The effectiveness of songs in increasing student participation as an interactive learning method has also been noted. Studies show that children better remember language units through musical rhythm and melody. According to Howard Gardner's multiple intelligence theory, children with developed musical intelligence can achieve faster results in language learning through songs. Also, according to Krashen's "Affective Filter Hypothesis," songs help students reduce psychological pressure and organize the language learning process in a comfortable environment for them.

Advantages of using songs in elementary school

Songs are an important tool for developing children's pronunciation and phonetic skills, that is, improving pronunciation and mastering intonation. Rhythmic structure and repetitive phrases in songs help to pronounce sounds correctly. In addition, with the help of songs, it is possible to expand vocabulary, that is, in

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songs, children easily assimilate phrases and words used in everyday life. In particular, topics such as colors, numbers, animal names, greetings, and farewells are easily taught through songs. Also, songs help to improve the ability to listen and remember. Because the words and phrases in them are memorized with musical rhythm, children remember them for a long time. Most importantly, the songs engage students in interactive communication. Through singing songs, children increase their confidence in communicating in a foreign language, and through them, children become acquainted with the culture of different peoples. This expands their worldview and develops their intercultural communication skills.

Methodology of using songs

For the effective use of songs in teaching English in primary grades, it is important to consistently implement several stages. These stages help students thoroughly master new language material and apply it in the process of communication. The first is the preparatory stage, that is, students are briefly informed about the theme of the song and the new words encountered in it are explained. At this stage, the main themes of the song are explained - for example, everyday topics such as nature, animals, family, colors, numbers, or greetings. Also, new words and phrases encountered in the song text are explained in advance, and their pronunciation is correctly studied. This preparatory stage is important so that students do not encounter misunderstandings while listening to the song.

The second is listening and singing, that is, students listen to the song and then sing it together. It is recommended to listen to the song several times to understand its overall meaning. In the next stage, the children sing the song together with the teacher. As a result of learning in a rhythmic and melodic style, children remember words and phrases more easily. If the song is performed together with movements during the singing process, the process of students' understanding and memorization of the song's content will be more effective.

Third, analysis and understanding, that is, the text of the song is discussed, the meaning of words and phrases is explained. At this stage, students learn the main words and phrases of the song more deeply. Grammatical structures taken from the song are explained and reinforced with examples. The teacher can ask the children questions about the content of the song or organize a short conversation about the song. Thus, students not only memorize and sing the song, but also begin to understand its content.

Fourthly, at the stage of practical exercises, students perform various practical exercises based on songs. For example, role-playing games, that is, they perform small scenes corresponding to the content of the song. Or motor exercises, that is, performing movements corresponding to the lyrics of the song, for example, reinforce the words through physical movements. In addition, it is possible to work with pictures and cards, that is, to select or correctly place pictures that correspond to the words and phrases of the song. Also, with the help of exercises to fill the space, some words from the song text are removed, and students try to memorize and fill them. Practical exercises allow children to understand the song more deeply and actively use newly learned language units. With the help of this method, students actively participate in the process of language acquisition and quickly memorize the studied material.

Conclusion

The use of songs in teaching English in primary grades is one of the effective methods. The results of the study show that songs contribute to the development of students' linguistic skills, increase their speech activity, and make the process of learning a foreign language interesting. Through songs, students easily memorize new words and phrases, improve pronunciation and intonation, and increase their confidence in communication. Also, songs are important in strengthening students' hearing abilities, increasing their motivation for language, and organizing the interactive learning process. The study revealed that the educational effectiveness of songs depends on their correct selection and methodological application. Therefore, teachers should select songs in accordance with the age characteristics of students and the level of language learning. In general, the use of songs serves to make the process of mastering English by primary school students more effective. Therefore, it is recommended to widely implement this methodological approach in primary education programs.

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